

Invitation to the Final Conference of the AGRIGEP Project

PRESS RELEASE, Prague, 19 September 2025

*The Czech University of Life Sciences Prague invites media representatives to the **Final Conference of the international project AGRIGEP, which will take place on 25 September 2025** from 9:00. The conference emphasizes that gender equality is a key prerequisite for innovation, competitiveness, and academic excellence. The event will showcase practical examples, open discussions on lessons learned, and focus on stakeholder engagement strategies that lead to real change. Experiences from sister projects and EU-level experts will enrich policy recommendations and empower actors in creating an inclusive academic and professional environment. The event will take place in a hybrid format – with the possibility of both in-person and online participation.*

The aim of the AGRIGEP Final Conference is to summarize the experiences gained during the implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) at universities of agriculture and life sciences in Central and Eastern Europe. As the culmination of a three-year project, the event will bring together educators, policymakers, researchers, students, and practitioners to identify persisting challenges and seek future pathways toward sustainable institutional transformation.

The title of the roundtable, *“Advancing Gender Equality in Academia for Sustainability, Excellence, Competitiveness and Economic Growth in Europe”*, highlights that gender equality in science is not only a matter of fairness, but also a key prerequisite for sustainable development, scientific excellence, competitiveness, and economic growth in Europe. An important part of the program will be dedicated to recommendations for future policy, practice, and institutional change. For the first time, the conference will also host a discussion among university representatives who will exchange experiences on implementing inclusive policies in academia, addressing barriers in this process, and sharing good practices to inspire other institutions.

Speakers will include representatives of the European Commission, Czech and international ministries, universities, and research institutions, together with experts on gender equality.

“Equal opportunities and a fair and supportive approach to researchers at different stages of their careers are not only a formal obligation, but also a pathway to higher-quality research and a stronger sense of belonging in our institutions. However, the importance of these values, the specific measures, and the language through which we promote them must be constantly

reconsidered and openly discussed,” said Adéla Gjuričová, Director of the Institute of Contemporary History of the Czech Academy of Sciences and Vice-Chair of the Czech Government Council for Research, Development and Innovation, one of the conference speakers.

The conference will also provide a lively perspective from students through short presentations and posters. These contributions will showcase how the young generation of scientists perceives equality of opportunity and how they contribute to transforming the academic environment. For the media, the event offers attractive visual material and inspiring stories about the emerging new face of science and education.

The conference will feature:

- Opening ceremony and speeches by distinguished guests (e.g., representatives of ČZU, AGRIGEP project coordinator, representatives of the European Research Program)
- A keynote lecture on the importance of gender equality for academic excellence and innovation, delivered by Marcela Linková, Head of the Centre for Gender and Science at the Institute of Sociology, Czech Academy of Sciences, Co-Chair of the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality, an advisory body of the European Commission
- A roundtable and two expert panel discussions

Practical Information

- Date: 25 September 2025
- Venue: Faculty of Economics and Management, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague – Suchbát, Room D107
- Format: Hybrid (in-person and online)
- Registration and program: <https://agrigeu.eu/agrigeu-final-conference/>

- For further details, please contact:

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- **Follow the AGRIGEP project on social media:**

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